

Rediscovering legumes as functional crops in cropping systems

Problem

Legumes are often regarded as non-profitable crops due to their lower and highly volatile yield, due to pests and weed control.

Solution

Introducing legumes as part of a crop-rotation can supply a variety of benefits called “ecosystem services”; which could be more accurately quantified by assessing the legume impact over the whole crop rotation, rather than just as a single crop.

Benefits

Legumes in crop-rotation systems provide a suite of ecosystem benefits, including improvements in crop diversification, encouraging natural nutrient cycling, reducing pollution, and supporting pollinating, and other beneficial insects.

Applicability box

Theme

Ecosystem services provision

Keywords

Ecosystem service benefits; legumes; cover crops;

Context

Europe

Application time

Throughout the year

Required time At least several months, depending on the specific practice.

Period of impact

Throughout the season and in the following seasons.

Equipment

Standard farm equipment.

Best in

Any cropping systems

Practical recommendation

Use leguminous main crops and cover crops as a:

- ‘green manure’ prior to high nitrogen (N)-fertiliser demanding crops (Figure 1a);
- sacrificial green manure, grown then mown between cash-crop (cereal) rows (Figure 1b); and,
- prior to high nitrogen (N) fertiliser demanding crops (Figure 1c).

Figure 1. A. Triticale -hairy vetch winter cover crops to control soil erosion, nitrate leaching and increasing N availability in the soil; B. Temporary cropping with chickpea, lupin and hairy vetch to increase nutrient supply in durum wheat; and C. Pea and faba bean in pea-wheat-chickpea-wheat rotation and in a faba bean-wheat rotation to increase nutrient supply to wheat.

About this practice abstract

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LegumES – Valorization of ecosystem services provided by legume crops - aims to share, showcase, co-develop, and implement the knowledge, key agronomic practices, methodologies, and tools which will allow optimized legume-based systems, and valorization of the ES benefits provided.
Project website: www.legumesproject.eu

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